

Ayurvedic Management of Trigeminal Neuralgia (Anantvat): A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Trigeminal neuralgia is a chronic neuropathic pain involving the trigeminal nerve which is responsible for sudden, abrupt, and recurrent episodes of sharp burning-like / electric shock-like feeling on one side of the face which lasts for a few minutes. In some cases, it may persist for a day or two. This condition can be correlated with Anantavata mentioned in Sushruta Samhita Shiroroga Adhayaya. It is a Vata-dominant tridoshaja shiroroga but with a good prognosis. This case is about a 67-year-old female with trigeminal neuralgia manifestations for the last 8–9 years following brain tumour surgery. Based on the classical symptoms, she was diagnosed as Anantavata in my clinic and Ayurvedic medications were started. She was treated with oral intake of Panchamrita Loha Guggulu, Dasmoola Quath, Aswagandha choorna, and Ekangavir Rasa. Ksheerabala 101 capsule was added later for Abhyantara snehana purpose. The result was satisfactory with complete cessation of symptoms. The duration of initial medication was 30 days. Pain and other complaints were recorded before and after treatment using the VAS Pain Scale..

Keywords: Anantavata, Shiroroga, Trigeminal neuralgia, Neuropathic facial pain, Ayurvedic management, VAS Pain scale, Case report

INTRODUCTION

Trigeminal neuralgia/tic duoloureux is a Neurological disorder characterized by recurrent episodes of intense stabbing /burning/pricking /electric shock like pain in the area in the face supplied by Trigeminal Nerve, the 5th CN and mostly in forehead, Cheek and lower Jaws. This is famously called as “lightning bolt “to the face. Generally, one side of face is involved mostly with V2(Maxillary) and V3(Mandibular)¹. This condition is mostly secondary to compression of Trigeminal Nerve root, with 80-90% cases the compression is by adjacent artery.^{2,3} The incidence is 4-13 peoples in every 100,000 annually.^{4,5} The life time prevalence is 0.16% -0.03%⁶ Its most common in females who are beyond their 4th or 5th decade of life. It is usually of two types, Type-1(Typical) and Type-2(Atypical). The

Type-1 is Characterized by abrupt and severe onset of sharp pain in parts of face which lasts for 2-10minutes⁷. The Atypical TN/Type-2 TN is characterized by constant burning /aching/Pricking pain with intensity which may last for few days.⁸ This current case is an Atypical TN. Right side of the face is 60% more affected than the left side. Bilateral simultaneous pain is rare.⁹

Some common drugs are used to treat these conditions Such as a) Antidepressants: Amitriptyline, Nortriptyline. b) Anti-Convulsant: Carbamazepine, Carbamazepine, Lamotrigine.c) Muscle relaxants: Baclofen d) Others: Gabapentin, Pregabalin etc.¹⁰ These drugs can have their various degrees of effectiveness and potential side effects. Where drugs are not in options, then Gamma Knife radio surgery

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/blocking of nerve is the last option¹¹ but with limited success.

The present case report is an attempt showcase the efficacy of Ayurvedic management of *Anantavata*. *Vata shamaka chikitsa by santarpana* is done in this case. Many case reports on Ayurvedic management of TN has been published and marked here.^{12,13}

Demographic Information:

Age 67 years

Sex: Female old lady suffering from TN since last 8-9 years

Occupation: House wife.

Chief Complaints:

Sudden and severe stabbing/burning/Electric shock like pain is reported on the left temporal area covering forehead and Cheek since last 4-5 years.

Medical History:

The elderly lady was diagnosed with brain tumour i.e. right CP Angle Schwannoma in 2014 and successfully operated in a NABH accredited hospital. 4-5 years after surgery of brain tumour she got periodic attacks of TN which made her irritable and quality of life deteriorated. Sleep was disturbed. She consulted various Modern system Allopathy physicians and contemporary medicines were advised. Initially she got bit result but after a period of time, those medicines seem less effective or ineffective.

Diet is mixed. Life style was less hectic as an elderly lady.

Past History: H/o- Right CP Angle Schwannomas (Brain tumour) and its surgical intervention in 2014

Co Morbidities: Diabetes Mellitus Type-2 since last 8-10 years with Hypertension, on relevant modern medications and it is under good control.

Personal History:

Diet: Mixed, Appetite: Moderate, Bowel Habit: Regular, Sleep: Disturbed, Mental status: Bit irritated, Wt:77kg, Life style: Less hectic

Family history/Genetic History: No one in her family was ever suffered from such conditions

Past Intervention: Post operatively she was given Oxetal 300 mg (Oxcarbazepine) for Trigeminal neuralgia and it was working initially but after 4-5 years its result reduced bringing much discomfort to the patient thereafter.

Time line:

2013 Sept: Occasional headaches with vomiting & hearing loss (right ear)

2014 June: MRI done, right CP Angle acoustic Schwannoma with hydrocephalus detected and operated.

2019: Reported for TN and Tab Oxetal started.

2023 March: ENT consultation for hearing loss in rt side ear & audiometry evaluation

2024 May: Ananata vata diagnosed and ayurvedic intervention started.

2024 June: 1st follow up with 60% reduced complaints.

2024 August: 2nd Follow up with 85% reduced complaints.

Investigation:

1. Audiology evaluation:

2. MRI (Techniques used) DWI, T1, T2 & FLAIR Axials, T2 Sagittal & Coronal. Post Contrast fat sat: T1 axial Coronal, & Sagittal.

Result:

1. Bilateral severe sensory neural deafness and using hearing aid since

2. 11x15x14 mm brilliantly enhancing extra axial mass lesion at the Right CP angle minimally extending into interior auditory canal, compressing

the Origin of 5thCN and adjacent pons. Mild cerebral atrophy.

Diagnosis: *Anantavata*/Trigeminal neuralgia based on questionnaires and MRI

Diagnostic Challenges: Did not come across any as patient was financially stable

Diagnostic reasoning:

1. Diabetic neuropathy/*Vataja Vikara*

2. *Ardhabavhedaka*

3. *Ananta vata*.

Samprapti Ghataka of *Anantavata*:

Nidana: Exposure to Cold air, Irregular lifestyle, Mental stress, Ageing

Dosha :*Vata pradhanya Tridosha*.

Dushya:*Majja,Snyau,Rakta,Rasa*,

Shrotos:*Rasa vaha,Rakta vaha,Majja vaha*.

Roga marga:Madhayama.

Adhithana:Sira,Kapola,Karna,Netra.

Samprapti Ghataka: Vata dusti due to Dhatu Kshaya & Margabarana.

Therapeutic intervention: Pharmacological intervention form of classical Ayurveda drugs was advised for the patient.

1.*Panchamrita Louha Guggulu*:250mg tabs thrice daily for 30 days.

2.*Dasmoola Quath* 15ml twice daily after food for 30days.

3.*Ksheeravala 101* capsules: one cap thrice daily for 30 days.

4.*Ekanga veera Rasa* 250mg tabs twice daily after food 30 days.

5.*Aswagandha Choorna* 3gm twice daily for 30 days.

Sr No.	Name of the Preparation	Key Ingredients	Reference
1	<i>Panchamrit Loha Guggulu</i>	<i>Suddha Parada,Suddha Gandhak, Kantaloha Bhasma</i> .	<i>Bhaisajya Ratnavali</i> .
2	<i>Dasmoola Quath</i>	<i>Laghu and Brihat Panchamula</i> .	
3	<i>Ksheeravala 101 capsules</i>	<i>Bala (Sida cordifolia Linn. roots, (Family: Malvaceae), Cow milk (Godugdha), Tila taila (Sesame Oil)</i>	<i>Astanga. Hridaya</i>
4	<i>Ekangaveer Rasa Anupana:Rasnadi Quath</i> .	<i>Suddha Gandhak,Rasa Sindoor,K.Loha Bhasma,Vanga Bhasma,Trikatu Quath,Nirgundi Quath.Triphala,Chitraka,Shigru,Vishamusti</i>	<i>Brihat Nighantu Ratnakara</i> .
5	<i>Aswagandha Choorna</i> .	<i>Aswagandha root powder (Withania somnifera root)</i>	Ayurvedic Pharmacopeia Of India

Probable mode of action:

On *Dosha*: Pacifies Kapha & Vata by Snigdha & Ushma guna. Addresses Avarana.

On *Dushya*: Majja dhatu: Nourished by Abhraka, Lauha, and Guggulu

Rakta dhatu purification by Gandhaka Rasayana

On *Shrotos*: Opens obstructed Majjavaha and Raktavaha Srotas

Enhances cellular metabolism through Trikatu

On *Rogamarga*: Nervous system (Brain) & deeper tissues.

Neurovascular action: Neuro protective due to presence of Abharaka Bhasma & Guggula helps to re-myelination and nervous conduction.

Ama & Inflammation: Removes Ama & clears inflammation due to Guggulu, Triphala & Trikatu.

Rasayana effect: Triphala & Guggulu effected Rasayana karma by improving Majja & Oja.

Changes in Intervention:

No change in intervention after 1st follows up after 30 days as results were promising. Same drug continued for 2 months.

Follow up and outcomes:

Clinician and patient assessed outcomes: The patient is very relaxed and seems happy with the results. Pain scale is assessed with VAS (Visual Analogue Scale). It has five grades, No pain, Mild, Moderate, Intense and Unspeakable. The marking by score from 1(No pain) to 10(Unspeakable Pain).

Important follow up Test results:

Sr No	Before Treatment	Score before Treatment	Score after Treatment	Follow up After 60 days
1	Pain over temporal area	8	1	1
2	TMJ Stiffness	2	1	0
3	Pain over cheeks	8	2	0

Intervention adherence and Tolerability: Intervention was good and tolerance was excellent.

Adverse and Unanticipated events: None reported.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION:

The patient was asked to come for 1st follow up after taking above mentioned Ayurvedic drugs for 30 days. The patient was uncomfortable with *nasya* so it was avoided here. In *vata vyadhi chikitsa Sutra*, *Sodhana Chikitsa* is advised along with Rasayana (Reference). But due to patient had good/normal bowel evacuation regularly we had altogether omitted it from treatment protocol. After 30 days on 1st follow up, she was feeling bit relaxed and pain was reduced to some good extent. Due to reduced attacks, she could sleep properly. *Panchamrita loha Guggulu*, *Dasamoola Quath* and other medicines were continued for 30 days. 2nd follow up was planned after 30 days post 1st follow up. On 2nd follow up the patient was in good condition and pain and attacks were reduced to great extent. The result was graded in VAS scale and shown earlier in table form.

Discussion: *Anantavata* is a *vata* predominant *tridoshaja Sadhya Shiro roga*. Here main *dosha* is *vata* so *Dasamoola Quath* is given as its *shoola nashaka*. *Vata shaman* also lead to *Agnee Vriddhi*.

Aswagandha Choorna is *brimhana dravya* which can bring good sleep. It has soothing effect on nervous system. *Ekangavir Rasa* is *brimhana* and *vata shaman*. *Ksheeravala 101* capsules contain *Godugdha* and *bala moola*, and *tila* which are again *madhura*, *guru*, *snigdha*. So, this ingredient is best for *Abhyantara Snehana*, as per treatment Principles of *Vata Vyadhi*¹². *Panchamrita loha Guggulu* is analgesic, nerve tonic, muscle relaxant and *shulahara*. So, all these drugs pacify *vata* and hence the pain of *Ananta Vata* is pacified. Here *sodhana Chikitsa* could not be employed due to higher age of patient.

CONCLUSION:

The disease *Ananta vata* is a *tridoshaja sadhya vata Vyadhi* which is to be managed with *Vata shamaka*, *brimhana* method and *Rasayana Dravya*. These employed formulations acted as nerve tonic, muscle relaxant and analgesic and *Rasayana* (*Rejuvenator*) which is perfect recipe for the treatment of *Ananta Vata*.

Informed Consent: Not requested and not necessary as patient's identity is kept confidential.

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